

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DUNCAN****FIRST NAME: JOHN****PROGRAM CODE: MTSD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. COPPINI****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Discipline in writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. American and British writing styles (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
4. Academic writing as compared to creative writing (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)
5. Research (EUCLID 2021, 8-9)

WRITING A GOOD RESPONSE PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

I was at first reluctant to re-enter academia as a student again. I spent nineteen years teaching at a college in Western North Carolina before I left to pursue other opportunities. I am creating and teaching classes for international students in my current position. Returning as a student in a graduate program at my age is an intimidating thing. Although I find the subject matter of my program fascinating, I almost declined the opportunity. My insecurity about academic writing almost exclusively caused my reluctance to join the program.

When I entered a graduate program for the first time, the English department at the university was extremely short-staffed due to phased retirements and hiring freezes. Consequently, I could not take a graduate-level writing class until my second semester. My first semester was an unmitigated disaster. My papers were returned for correction with more red ink on them than the black ink I printed them in. It was doubly distressing because I had just finished my Bachelor's degree in English with a creative writing focus. I assumed that writing would not be a problem for me. I was incredibly wrong.

Barely surviving my thesis production emotionally, I resolved to avoid academic writing in the future. The Army changed that plan for me. Once I was promoted to Major, I attended professional development classes that required me to produce papers at the graduate level, which meant I had to re-learn the academic writing process.

2) DISCIPLINE IN WRITING

The ACA-401 coursepack for period 1 (EUCLID 2021) stresses the importance of starting an essay early and not procrastinating. As a professor, I was constantly amazed by students who only started papers the last few days before they was due. “It is not due for a week, I still have plenty of time,” was a statement I would hear throughout my career. From my creative writing experience, I knew this “last second” approach guaranteed poor results. Time management is not as simple as starting a project when it is first assigned. Time must be allocated appropriately within the project. Cleenewerck and Gulma discuss the importance of proper research (EUCLID 2021, 7-9). Allocating enough time for research can be difficult when you do not understand the scope of research available. The lesson, chapter, or textbook may be sufficient for a simple response paper. For a master’s thesis paper, the literature review might take weeks, and a doctoral dissertation may require months!

Time is not the only element of discipline required for success. The writer must maintain consistency across the work. Consistency in mechanics such as font size and style must be maintained, but tone and voice should also remain constant throughout the work. Shifts in tone can be jarring to the reader and take away from the impact of the work. Maintaining a consistent tone is one of the best ways to ensure a smooth flow to the paper.

3) AMERICAN AND BRITISH WRITING STYLES

Being born and raised in the American south, traveling with the military, and spending over twenty years in the Appalachian region has given me an understanding of accents, dialects, and writing differences in American English. There are vast differences in expressions, slang, and profanity from region to region. As a native of the United States, I believe that the American style is the best, but as a reasonable person I must respect that a native of London would feel the same about their way. However, since I am a native to one system, I am not in the more challenging situation that some students who are non-native speakers of either dialect will encounter. Since I am proficient in the American style, I will stick to the conventions of that system as outlined in the coursepack (EUCLID 2021, 24-32).

4) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is intellectual theft. It is stealing from the minds of others. It is a sign of laziness and an inability to capture one’s thoughts compellingly. Cleenewerck and Gulma

define plagiarism as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 34). Plagiarism is one of the most severe offenses in academia. In America today is quite difficult to get removed from college. Short of criminal activity, most students are repeatedly given chances to correct their behavior. I have seen students removed from programs of study over plagiarism. This effectively terminated their ability to study in their chosen field. I have also seen people expelled from service academies and denied a military commission over incidents of plagiarism.

Allegations of plagiarism can follow a person throughout their lives and may hold serious consequences in their professional life. During the 1987 run-up to the American presidential election, Joe Biden was forced to withdraw from the race when it was revealed that he plagiarized elements of his campaign speech (Simon 2015). In 2012 the president of Hungary was forced to resign and had his doctorate rescinded after it was revealed that he had plagiarized significant portions of his dissertation (Fascar, 2012).

Plagiarism is easy to avoid but also easy to commit accidentally. Proper citation is the key to preventing plagiarism. Modern tools such as Zotero make it easy to use appropriate citations and avoid deliberate issues. I define unintentional plagiarism as when a writer inadvertently borrows tone or sentence structure from another author. One of my creative writing professors assigned my class to read three different anthologies of short stories by Earnest Hemmingway. Over half the class turned in papers that were either borderline cases of plagiarism or certain cases. Most did not mean to do wrong, but after so much exposure to a distinctive writing tone, many people copied it to one extent or another. Modern software such as Grammarly Premium help guard against this, but the final responsibility rests with the author.

5) ACADEMIC WRITING AS OPPOSED TO CREATIVE WRITING

Academic writing is significantly different from creative writing. One difference between the two that is immediately apparent is the level of research involved. In creative writing most authors are certainly not subject matter experts on the topics they write about. They do basic levels of research and consult experts to determine specific plot points, but most do not need to research deeply. Academic writing is designed to answer a question or lend support to (or disprove) a thesis. Complete and well-balanced research on a topic is expected, and conclusions are to be drawn. The primary purpose of creative writing is entertainment. A lesson may be taught, or a story told, but it is primarily a work of opinion, not fact. Creative writing does not need to be factual or balanced. It can be free form and has no obligation to conform to any stylistic norms. Academic writing should conform to international rules of style. EUCLID recommends the Turabian style (EUCLID 2021, 41). Creativity is critical in all forms of writing. In creative writing, it is used to design everything. All stories are created in the mind of the author. In academic writing, it explores new ideas discovered from research into a topic and designs the best way to format and display information.

6) RESEARCH

Research is the basis of academic writing. It is the frame that an author will build their agreement upon. Building upon already known information is a primary method of advancing human understanding. Using quality work done by others allows a researcher to develop new insights and further expand on the information already discovered.

The literature review phase of a thesis or dissertation gives the author a solid understanding of a subject and knowledge of current theories and previously discarded theories. This avoids accidental duplication of effort or going down paths discarded because of evidence. It identifies areas of research that have not been completely explored and where more exploration can add to the body of knowledge.

EUCLID recommends using all credible sources for information (EUCLID 2021, 9). It is essential to read all the information, not to give in to confirmation bias, and only look at data that agrees with your theory. Conflicting evidence or contrary opinions to the thesis should be addressed, to include the major points of those dissenting views. Any new evidence that disproves or minimizes the effect of conflicting information assists in supporting the thesis. Part of presenting a thesis is defending it.

7) CONCLUSION

As this class is foundational to my successful pursuit of a master's degree and eventual doctorate, I asked to be enrolled in the "D" variation. This is the one class I dread. No matter how necessary, I am intimidated by this class. I have never believed in rules-for-rules sake, and have always been interested in information transfer and unconcerned about the format in which the information is transmitted. This mindset caused me constant trouble in graduate school, causes me ongoing problems in the Army, and is something I will have to overcome as I return to graduate studies. Hopefully, I will be able to use this class to create new habits and set myself up for success moving forward.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Fascar, Fanny. 2012. "Hungary's President Quits over Alleged Plagiarism." CNN, April 2, 2012. <https://www.cnn.com/2012/04/02/world/europe/hungary-president-resigns/index.html>.

Simon, Jeff. 2015. "A Peek at Joe Biden's Past Presidential Campaigns | CNN Politics." CNN. October 21, 2015. <https://www.cnn.com/2015/10/21/politics/joe-biden-presidential-campaigns-1988-2008/index.html>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.